

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Customer Relationship Management Strategy and Organizational Performance of Cadbury Nigeria Plc, Lagos State

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) strategy and organizational performance of Cadbury Nigeria plc. Lagos State. The objectives of the study were to determine the relationship between customer knowledge management capability, customer interaction management capability, customer win-back capability, and customer patronage in Cadbury Nigeria plc. In the study, a descriptive survey design was adopted. The sources of data for the study were employees of Cadbury Nigeria plc. Lagos State. The arithmetic means standard deviation and t-test were used for analyzing data. In the study, organizational performance was measured by customer patronage, while dimensions/strategies of Customer Relationship Management measured were customer knowledge management capability (CKMC), customer interaction management capability (CIMC), and customer win-back capability (CWC). Results of analyses showed a positive significant relationship between customer knowledge management capability and customer patronage (t-cal. = 0.197). A positive relationship was found between customer interaction management capability and customer patronage (t-cal. = 0.29). The findings also showed a positive relationship between customer win-back capability and customer patronage (t-cal. = 0.35). In the study, we concluded that Cadbury Nigeria plc was more likely to have improved organizational performance where CRM strategy was applied or adopted. The study, therefore, recommended that Cadbury Nigeria plc. Lagos should pay greater attention to the perceived value of its products by customers. Correspondingly, they should ensure that more priority was placed on responding to and dealing with the complaints of their customers. These would increase the continuous patronage of their customers and hence improve their performance

Keywords: *Customer Relationship Management Strategy; Organizational Performance; Cadbury Nigeria Plc*

Introduction

In today's business environment, relationship building is very essential for firms' survival, efficiency, performance, and competitiveness (Opaleye, Ojelade & Aremu, 2020). In today's dynamic, changing market, all companies and especially the food and beverage industries are influenced by what happens while attempting to retain their customers in the competitive market worldwide such as treating new customers better, prompt attendance to their complaints, appreciating their continuous patronage, along with similar services. This is because the growth of any business lies in the level of patronage of customers as regards their products (Arsson & Moez, 2017; Vecente, Hermenegildo, & Javier, 2021). Companies in the food and beverage sector do not only aspire to please consumers but they still try to fulfil their competitive business targets more effectively and efficiently than their rivals, to be on good terms with their customers (Hassan, Lashari & Zafar, 2020); Since marketing experts perceive the value of consumer loyalty, which refers to a customer's likelihood of repeating a business with a company or brand, arising from customer happiness, positive customer experiences, and the entire value of goods or services received by a customer from a company (Khan, Salamzadeh, Iqbal and Yong, 2020). The key aim of most companies in the food and beverage

industry is to retain client loyalty and emphasize a customer-centric approach to ensure that customers get essentially what they want. Such a situation leads to effective customer relationship management - building trust with the customers, over-delivering on customer promises, leveraging feedback, setting customer expectations, developing frequent communication, and offering customer services (Itani, Goad & Jaramilo, 2019).

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Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a method of controlling a company's interaction with existing and potential customers by establishing a trusting relationship. It focuses on the analysis of data and a review of the company's past to improve customer relationships, with a particular emphasis on customer satisfaction and, eventually, sales growth (Wongleedee, 2020). The value of customer satisfaction cannot be overlooked as the customer must become the focus of any company. The need and means of maintaining closer ties with customers are heralded by the constant growth of competition, dynamism and complex nature of doing business in the food and beverages industries, product brand, trust, price charge to commodities, motivation, after-sales service behaviour, etc., which may make it difficult for a customer to be lured to other brands (Johanesova & Vanova, 2020). The global food and beverage industry underwent a significant transformation in the last decade and the Nigerian food and beverage industry is no exception. Companies might create new products or services to meet a specific need in a target market. However, a product's success cannot be guaranteed unless the customer's opinion of the product is favourable. To address these trends and keep them competitive in the industry, customer-oriented strategies that seek to retain and enhance the loyalty and patronage of customers have become indispensable for the food and beverage production industries. Given the above background, the study was carried out to evaluate the relationship between customer relationship management strategy and organizational performance of food and beverage firms in Lagos State using Cadbury Nigeria Limited as a case study.

Statement of the Problem

Customer relationship management factors entail loyalty and patronage of the customer such as commitment, conflict handling, trust, communication, competency, after-sales service, brand perception, product, and so on. Some studies focused on the commitment of companies, trust, communication, empathy, fulfilling promises, and social bonding to measure CRM while some others measured the effects of CRM components on customer loyalty. Nigeria's food and beverages industry are growing in Nigeria, yet the level of failure in their services indicate that ineffective relationship with customer seems to be pronounced. Today, all businesses in the food and beverages sector are competing in different ways to attract the same consumers and keep them. As a result, building customer relationships become important. Based on the above, there are diverse measures of CRM which include several different components. The variety of CRM components targeted and thought to customer loyalty within the literature shows that several questions need to be addressed, such as; what component of CRM is deemed most important by customers? What is the relationship between CRM components and customer loyalty through patronage as well as what measures are relevant in measuring CRM?

The relationship between CRM components and customer patronage if not identified will ultimately affect the survival of Food and beverage companies. Empirical research exploring CRM and its relationship with customer loyalty and patronage might provide important information in this domain that may inform relevant CRM strategies, hence the need for this study.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study was to evaluate the relationship between customer relationship management strategy and the organizational performance of Cadbury Nigeria Limited, Lagos.

The specific objectives of the study were to:

- I. Examine the relationship between customer knowledge management capability (CKMC) and customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *p.l.c.* Lagos State.
- II. Ascertain the relationship between Customer Interaction Management Capability (CIMC) and customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *p.l.c.* Lagos State.
- III. Assess the relationship between Customer Win-back Capability (CWC) and customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *p.l.c.* Lagos State.

Statement of Hypotheses

The following alternate hypotheses were formulated to further guide the study:

- I. Customer Knowledge Management Capability (CKMC) has a relationship with customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *p.l.c.* Lagos State.
- II. Customer Interaction Management Capability (CIMC) has a relationship with customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *p.l.c.* Lagos State.

- III. Customer Win-back Capability (CWC) has a relationship with customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *p/c*. Lagos State.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Customer Relationship Management and its Dimensions

Customer relationship management is a term for handling the relationships of an organization with suppliers, customers, and sales opportunities, such as customer retention, loyalty, or satisfaction. It is a framework that uses the desires and practices of its consumers to build deeper relationships (Nasution & Rafiki, 2018). Bhakane, (2015) sees customer relationship management as an operational activity that involves the collection, analysis, and management of customers' information for better managing relationships between an organization and its customers to ensure that economic value that accrues to the customers during business interactions is amplified. At this juncture, the result of customer relationship management is to promote customer satisfaction and build loyalty over time. Another definition by Hammoud, Bizri and Baba (2018) described customer relationship management as an organizational process that encompasses the identification, segregation, and evaluation of customers based on their consumption habits to improve organizational products as well as perception.

For this study, customer relationship management is defined as a method of controlling a company's interaction via brand perception, product performance, organizational trust, complaint handling, and after-sale service (Lubis, Dalimunthe, Absah, and Fawzee, 2020). These components are important because they cover all areas in which most customers look to maintain continuous patronage of a company product. Moreover, most studies failed to look at all these components which make this study more comprehensive than previous studies.

Customer Knowledge Management Capability (CKMC) relates to all the actions and processes meant to get and analyze the information of customers, coming up with and dispersing in-depth knowledge of customers to create and maintain a portfolio of customer relationships to ensure greater profitability (Wang, 2012). Customer Interaction Management Capability (CIMC), is the ability of a firm to recognize, secure, keep, and partner with existing customers and prospective customers who are likely to be profitable. The skill required in CIMC entails recognizing, securing, keeping, and partnering with profitable clients is a major and critical success factor for every organization (Wang, 2012). Customer Win Back (CWC) on the other hand has to do with the process of reestablishing a relationship with customers who are lost or not active. Firms losing customers frequently will experience negative outcomes in performance (Wang, 2012).

Organizational Performance

Organizational performance is the ability of an organization to produce results. Abang and Maw (2016) attribute organizational performance to bottom-line profit, doing better than competitors, maximum organizational effectiveness, and achieving specific organizational objectives. Since the main goal of an organization is to satisfy the needs of customers it will lead to increased organizational performance. This indicates that without the existence of customers, business activities will be futile. Business owners often concentrate on the improvement of their products, this is one of the basic features of the production concept. Often, they ignore their customer care and relationship; as a result, many of their customers move their purchasing interests to organizations that can serve them better.

Customer Loyalty through Patronage

Customer loyalty is an important benchmark for a firm's continued increase in sales and overall corporate development. By patronizing the same brand and rejecting competitors' products, loyal customers provide a firm with a steady inflow of revenue, Haghkchah, Rasoolimanesh & Asgari (2020). Möslein-Tröppner, Stros, and Říha (2020) define loyalty as an ardent commitment to a particular brand often leading to a rebuy of a preferred product or service in the future, in the presence of externally influencing actions that may cause a brand substituting behaviour by the consumers. Customer loyalty can be connected to purchase frequency. Chih-Hung, Kuo-Min, and Santos (2019) see customer loyalty as identification with a brand or its products /service that induces continuous repurchases behaviours by the customer. Here, loyalty is seen as a commitment to repeat buying. Raza, Umer, Qureshi, and Dahri (2020) define customer loyalty as a customer's intention to repurchase a product/service and an intention to refer the product to others.

In recent times, due to the volatile nature of the economic market, it is almost impossible for businesses to succeed without putting the customer at the forefront of their management. As a result, companies' attention is increasingly

centred on how to please customers to retain their loyalty or repeated patronage (Lubis *et al.*, 2020). As a result, consumer satisfaction has been identified as one of the most significant determinants of potential product use by consumers (Ibrahim & Samuel, 2020). Customer satisfaction is also seen as a differentiating factor in a dynamic environment where companies compete for consumers as satisfaction is linked to customer loyalty. This concept has become a crucial feature of a business's strategy in that customer loyalty determines the reputation of the business and its products and or services in the minds of customers (Okereke & Okpe, 2020).

Haghkhah, Rasoolimanesh, and Asgari (2020) give three core areas of loyalty; Behavioral loyalty, attitudinal loyalty, and composite loyalty. Behavioural loyalty is a desire to continually repurchase a product /service from an organization coupled with a desire to maintain affiliation with the firm. On the other hand, attitudinal loyalty is a function of customers' psychological attachments to a brand. Attitudinal loyalty exists when a customer chooses to be loyal to the brand because of a distinct satisfaction accruing from utilizing the brand's products, thus necessitating a positive brand preference. Composite loyalty combines attitudinal and behavioural measures of loyalty and is considered to have better power in predicting customer behavioural purchase patterns. For this study, Raza *et al.* (2020) definitions are used. This definition is chosen because it goes in line with the view of this study as regards the loyalty of the customer.

Theoretical Framework

This study on the impact of CRM on customer loyalty is anchored on two theories. These are: (i). The Stakeholder Theory (ii). The Social Exchange theory

The Stakeholder Theory

This theory was developed by Donaldson in 1995. It asserts that organizations exist not only to maximize shareholder wealth but also to protect the interests of a wide range of stakeholders whose negative reactions could jeopardize the establishment's survival. The stakeholders include customers, employees, communities, suppliers, creditors as well as the government in the state.

Customers, according to stakeholder theory, are the lifeblood of any business since, without them, revenue cannot flow, and organizations would cease to exist. To optimize shareholder value, businesses must maintain a positive relationship with consumers, who are the primary source of revenue and the reason for their existence. That implies no customer, no business. The food and Beverages industries have a variety of ways to protect customers' interest, especially from external intruders or their competitors such as providing after-sales services, discounts for goods purchases, and end the promo, and putting in place stringent measures to ensure loyalty and confidence of the customer towards the product manufactured in their company. When a customer's interests are safeguarded, he will continue to purchase the company's products or services and will also suggest them to others. Mismanagement of a single customer can turn off a large number of potential customers. Therefore, because of its emphasis on customer relationship management, this theory is pertinent to this dissertation.

The Social Exchange Theory

This theory was developed by a sociologist named George Homans. It first appeared in 1958 in one of his essays titled "Social Behavior as Exchange. The core premise of Social Exchange Theory is that people make decisions by consciously or unconsciously weighing the costs and benefits of a relationship or activity, to maximize their reward. This idea focuses on one-on-one interactions and isn't intended to track societal behaviour or change. This suggests that a person will assess the cost of a social engagement against the benefit. These expenses and benefits can be monetary, time-based, or in the form of service. Intangibles such as effort, social approbation, love, pride, humiliation, respect, opportunity, and power are examples. Everyone wants to receive more out of a relationship or encounter than they put in. A person ends a relationship when it costs them more than it benefits them. However, they will sustain a relationship if it gives enough benefits. What is sufficient or insufficient is determined by a variety of factors, including the individual's expectations and comparisons to other possible interactions and partnerships. People anticipate equity in return, according to social exchange theory. People expect to be compensated equally for the same costs they incur, and they are disappointed when they are not.

The idea is now widely regarded as one of the most fundamental conceptual frameworks in the field of organizational behaviour. It proposed that being an active competitor (in the universal economy) necessitates being a trustworthy co-operator (in some networks). Furthermore, commitment and trust are the most important mediating factors because they drive trade partners to maintain relationship investments, reject appealing short-term replacements, and maintain the belief that partners would not act unethically. Trust may build as business

partners interact regularly. Therefore, since the Social Exchange Theory demonstrates how it could explain some human connections, such as interpersonal relationship growth, collective decision-making, and job performance (Redmond, 2015), the social exchange theory was increasingly significant in the study. The theory was significant as a theoretical framework for the study because it focused on the subject of customer relationship management.

Empirical Review

Bin-Nashwan and Hassan (2017) examined a systematic review on the impact of customer relationship management (CRM) on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The review was based on 35 articles published in a wide variety of journals and conferences between 2005 and 2015. The results found were diverse in terms of the publication trend, CRM classification, industries, and countries studied. The three dimensions that had been frequently used in prior studies that address the impact of CRM on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty were service quality (SQ), service access (SA), and handling complaints (HC). These factors were found to affect customer satisfaction and customer loyalty.

Waskito (2018) used domestic theory and regression analysis to examine the effect that customer relationship management has on the business's organizational profit. The study makes use of 420 respondents selected using convenience sampling techniques. He concluded that company profit increases with effective relationship management with the customer. The study also found that a significant positive relationship exists between CRM and the level of profit in the organization.

Chih-Hung, Kuo-Min, and Santos (2019) examined the effect of service recovery on customer loyalty based on marketing word of mouth in the tourism industry. The study administered a simple survey to 315 respondents in the tourism industry in Fujian province, China. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method of estimation techniques was used to analyze the data obtained from the response of the respondent. Their findings revealed that the service recovery of the organization impacted positively and significantly on the loyalty of the customer in their continuous patronage of the product of the organization.

Bukola, Abosede, and Adesola (2019) assessed the influence of customer relationship management on the performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Oyo state, Nigeria. A purposive sample technique was adopted to collect primary data from 100 participants from 20 SMEs within four local governments in Oyo state. The study employed the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method of estimation in analyzing the data collected from the respondent. Their findings show that customer relationship management has positively influenced the performances of SMEs in Oyo state.

Akpoviro, Amos, Oladipo, and Adewale (2020) assessed whether product quality has a significant impact on the loyalty of customers in the telecommunication industry in Nigeria. He limited the study to three major telecommunication industries which include Globacom, Airtel, and MTN in Lagos. A survey research design was adopted in selecting a total of 120 respondents. Analysis of variance and correlation techniques were employed. Their findings revealed that in the telecommunication company product branding has a significant impact on a product and helps in ensuring customer loyalty in the business. Also, a significant relationship exists in the telecommunication industry between product branding and the loyalty of consumers. The study however was based on telecommunication companies and not on food and beverage companies that are fast growing in Nigeria.

Itai and Onamusi (2020) studied the relationship between customer relationship management and customer loyalty in Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. The study employed a simple random sampling technique to sample a total of 1,019 bank customers. A well-structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data using a cross-sectional survey of 1,019 bank customers. Ordinary Least Squared (OLS) estimation techniques were employed in analyzing the data received from the administered questionnaire. Their findings revealed that customer relationship management had a significant and positive effect on customer loyalty in the Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

Methodology

A survey design was adopted. Survey research design is a quantitative method and an especially useful approach when a researcher aims to describe or explain features of a very large group or groups. The survey method was preferred because it ensured a complete description of the situation with minimum bias. Surveys are useful in describing the characteristics of a large population and ensuring the economy in the use of resources. The survey was adopted mainly because the researcher had no control over the variables in the study. The study was based on Cadbury Nigeria plc. located in Lagos, Nigeria. The study adopted a primary source of data from the Firm. The study population consisted of employees from different departments of the companies. The study employed the

questionnaire designed to be answered in a five-point Likert scale format as the instrument for data collection for this research work. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation and t-test at a 0.05 level of significance. The formula for the t-test is expressed mathematically as

$$t = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu_0}{s/\sqrt{n}}$$

Where;

\bar{x} = Observed Mean of the Sample

μ = Theoretical Mean of the Population

s = Standard Deviation of the Sample

n = Sample Size

Decision Rule: The decision rule is that if t-calculated is \geq t-tabulated, we reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternate hypotheses.

Taro Yamane's formula for estimating sample size was applied to determine the study sample. This is shown below. To determine the sample size (n)

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

e = max acceptable error = 5%

1 = Mathematical constant

N = population size = 1200

$$n = \frac{1200}{(1 + 1200)(0.05)^2} = \frac{1200}{1 + (1200 \times 0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{1200}{1 + (3)} = \frac{1200}{4}$$

$$n = 300$$

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data Presentation

Table 1: Responses on Customer Knowledge Management Capability

S/N	Items	Mean	STD.DEV	Remark
1.	My organization has a formal system for identifying potential customers	2.10	1.08	Disagreed
2.	In product introduction, customer information is usually applied	2.75	1.15	Agreed
3.	My organization considers customers' needs and expectations for the introduction of new products	3.32	0.87	Agreed
4.	My organization often uses customers to test and evaluate new products	3.24	0.81	Agreed
5.	My organization has means of identifying potential and valuable customers	2.20	0.99	Disagreed
	Grand Mean	2.72	0.98	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 2: Responses on Customer Interaction Management Capability

S/N	Items	Mean	STD.DEV	Remark
1.	My company develops strategies that can be used to determine customers' needs for new products.	2.43	1.08	Disagreed
2.	My organization has means of developing excellent relationships with important customers	3.56	0.79	Agreed
3.	My organization creates an avenue for effective communication with customers	3.17	0.72	Agreed
4.	My organization has a formal avenue for continuous dialogue aimed at improving customer relationship	2.32	1.01	Disagreed
5.	My organization has a strategy for maintaining relationships with important customers	2.87	0.97	Agreed
	Grand Mean	2.87	0.91	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 3: Responses on Customer win-back Capability

S/N	Items	Mean	STD.DEV	Remark
1.	My organization usually pays customers compensation for inconveniences	3.19	0.82	Agreed
2.	We have a systematic process/approach used to establish relationships with valued customers	3.07	0.62	Agreed
3.	We take corrective actions when customers are unhappy with the appropriateness of our products or service.	3.25	0.97	Agreed
4.	My organization maintain positive relationships with migrating or unattractive customer regularly	2.28	1.06	Disagreed
5.	We provide current customers with incentives for acquiring new potential	2.92	0.75	Agreed
	Grand Mean	2.94	0.84	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Data Analysis

Table 1 revealed that the respondents agreed to all items except items 1(2.10, 1.08) and 5(2.20, 0.99). The standard deviation ranged from 0.81 to 1.15 implying that the mean responses were not far from each other. With the grand mean score of 2.72 exceeding the statistical benchmark of 2.50 set, it can be concluded that Customer Knowledge Management Capability (CKMC) has a great effect on customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *plc*.

Table 2 revealed that the respondents agree with all items except iitems1(2.43, 1.08) and 4(2.32, 1.01). The standard deviation ranged from 0.72 to 1.08 indicating that the mean responses were not far from each other. Also, the grand mean score of 2.87 exceeded the statistical benchmark of 2.50 set. It can be deduced that Customer Interaction Management Capability (CIMC) is of great effect on customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *plc*.

Table 3 above showed that the respondents agreed to all items except item 4(2.28, 1.06). The standard deviation ranged from 0.62 to 1.06 indicating that the mean responses were not far from each other. The Grand mean score of 2.94 exceeded the statistical benchmark of 2.50 set.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 4: Relationship between Customer Knowledge Management Capability (CKMC) and Customer Patronage of Cadbury Nigeria plc.

Variables	Mean	SD	N	Df	t-cal.	t-tab.	P-value	Decision
CKMC	11.59	1.82	300	299	0.197	0.113	0.002	Ho is Rejected
Customer Patronage	12.13	2.47						

Table 4 reveals that the calculated 't' value (t-cal. = 0.197) is greater than the 't' tabulated (t-tab. = 0.113) at a 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis which says that Customer Knowledge Management Capability (CKMC) has no significant relationship with customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria Limited is rejected. It then means that Customer Knowledge Management Capability (CKMC) and customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria plc. had a significant positive relationship

Table 5: Relationship between Customer Interaction Management Capability (CIMC) and Customer Patronage of Cadbury Nigeria plc.

Variables	Mean	SD	N	Df	t-cal.	t-tab.	P-value	Decision
CIMC	18.56	2.68	300	299	0.29	0.113	0.003	Ho is Rejected
Customer Patronage	12.13	2.47						

P<0.05

Table 5 shows that the calculated 't' value (t-cal. = 0.29) is greater than the 't' tabulated (t-tab. = 0.113) at a 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis which says that there is no significant relationship between Customer Interaction Management Capability (CIMC) and customer patronage is rejected. It then means that Customer Interaction Management Capability (CIMC) and customer patronage have a significant relationship.

Table 6: Relationship between Customer Win-back Capability (CWC) and Customer Patronage of Cadbury Nigeria plc.

Variables	Mean	SD	N	Df	t-cal.	t-tab.	P-value	Decision
CWC	9.93	2.72	300	299	0.35	0.113	0.003	Ho is Rejected
Customer Patronage	12.13	2.47						

P<0.05

Table 6 reveals that the calculated 't' value (t-cal. = 0.35) is greater than the 't' tabulated (t-tab. = 0.113) at a 0.05 level of significance, hence, the null hypothesis which says that there is no significant relationship between Customer Win-back Capability (CWC) and customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria Limited is rejected. It then means that Customer Win-back Capability (CWC) and customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria Limited have a significant relationship.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the test of hypothesis one shows that Customer Knowledge Management Capability (CKMC) and customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *plc.* had a significant relationship. The t-calculated 0.197 is greater than the t-critical 0.113 at a 0.05 level of significance. This implied that gathering and analyzing customers' information and coming up with in-depth knowledge has a great influence on customer loyalty. The finding aligns with Katarzyna and Anna's (2019) submission that customer knowledge management capabilities and the business performance had a positive relationship with each other. The finding is also in tandem with Muhammad, Naveed, Haider, and Alamdar (2015) that if customer knowledge management capabilities are increased then organizational performance will increase automatically in a positive manner.

The result of the second hypothesis revealed that Customer Interaction Management Capability (CIMC) and customer patronage have a significant relationship. The t-calculated 0.29 is greater than the t-critical 0.113 at a 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the ways and manner an organization recognizes, secures, keeps, and relates to existing customers and prospective customers play crucial roles in organization development or profit maximization. This agreed with Mack (2015) who concluded that to enhance customer loyalty, a firm needed to recognize, secure, keep, and partner with existing and prospective customers.

The result of the third hypothesis tested showed that Customer Win-back Capability (CWC) and customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria Limited have a significant relationship. The t-calculated 0.35 is greater than the t-critical 0.113 at a 0.05 level of significance. This implied that re-establishing a good relationship with customers who are lost or not active would go a long way in improving the growth and survival of an organization. This aligns with Yun and Good (2017) who studied the impact of CRM on organization performance using a hierarchical construct model in which their results revealed a positive and significant path between a superior customer win-back capability and customer loyalty.

Summary of Findings

The major findings of the study included the following:

- I. Customer Knowledge Management Capability (CKMC) had a significant positive relationship with customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *plc.* Lagos.
- II. Customer Interaction Management Capability (CIMC) had a significant positive relationship with customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *plc.* Lagos.
- III. Customer Win-back Capability (CWC) had a significant positive relationship with customer patronage of Cadbury Nigeria *plc.* Lagos.

Conclusion

The study evaluated customer relationship management strategy and relationship with performance (customer patronage) of Cadbury Nigeria *plc.* Lagos, Lagos State. It was concluded that effective and proactive CRM played a pivotal role in the performance of Cadbury Nigeria *plc.* Lagos.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion above, the following recommendations were made:

- I. Cadbury Nigeria *plc.* Lagos should ensure that more priority was placed on responding to and dealing with the complaints of their customers as complaints handling was noted as a very important component of CRM by customers. This should be done by first identifying the major sources leading to customer dissatisfaction.
- II. Cadbury Nigeria *plc.* Lagos should pay more attention to the image of their product to potentially increase customers' repurchasing of more products and their recommendations of the brand to others.
- III. Cadbury Nigeria *plc.* Lagos should pay greater attention to the perceived value of its products to customers.

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